

Event title	WEBINAR: KBase - A knowledge base for systems biology
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	22/09/2021
Time of event	9am - 10am AEST
Topic description	<p>Developed for bench biologists and bioinformaticians, The Department of Energy Systems Biology Knowledgebase (KBase) is a free, open source, software and data science platform designed to meet the grand challenge of systems biology: predicting and designing biological function.</p> <p>This webinar will provide an overview of the KBase mission and user community, as well as a tour of the online platform and basic functionality. You'll learn how KBase can support your research: Upload data, run analysis tools (Apps), share your analysis with collaborators, and publish your data and reproducible workflows. We'll highlight a brand new feature that enables users to link environment and measurement data to sequencing data. You'll also find out how KBase supports findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) research by providing open, reproducible, shareable bioinformatics workflows.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/kbase
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Keywords	<p>Systems Biology http://edamontology.org/topic_2259 Metagenomics http://edamontology.org/topic_3174 FAIR Research Open Source Software Data analysis Microbiome</p>
Contact	Melissa Burke (melissa@biocommons.org.au)

Audience	Life science researchers interested in hearing about KBase.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Describe KBase• Outline methods for data upload, analysis and sharing
Webinar presenters	Ellen Dow, PhD - KBase Communications and Outreach Specialist Elisha Wood-Charlson, PhD - KBase User Engagement Lead
Related work	Not applicable